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the concentration of the alkali and hence the order with respect to the alkali concentration is unity.

The effect of varying ionic strength was also investigated by adding potassium chloride. The rate of the reaction was found to be increased with the increase of the ionic strength of the medium, which is a dominant characteristic of ion-ion reaction. The reaction has been studied in various methanol-water binary mixtures. The decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium results in a decrease in the rate constant. This supports the evidences in favour of the ion-ion reaction.

The reaction was studied in three different temperatures and the activation parameters were evaluated (Table 1).

Kinetics of Oxidation of Aromatic Ketones by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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POTASSIUM ferricyanide is classified as an oxidising agent in which the oxidising species is a complex electron-abstracting ion¹ and the reactions are thought to proceed by a radical mechanism². The kinetics of oxidation of a number of organic compounds by hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied by a number of workers³⁻⁶, though similar studies on aromatic ketones are not many. Speakman and waters⁷ have studied the kinetics of oxidation of aldehydes, ketones and nitroparaffins with alkaline ferricyanide. We have reported the oxidation of aromatic ketones by Mn(III)⁸, Ti(III)⁹, Cr(VI)¹⁰ and K₂S₂O₈¹¹. The present investigation deals with the oxidation of acetophenone and some ketones of the naphthalene series.

The ketones, acetophenone, 1-acetylnaphthalene and 2-acetylnaphthalene were used, were of B.D.H. (A.R.) grade and were purified as described earlier¹². The kinetics of these oxidations were studied in 30% (V) methanol-water mixture in alkaline medium at constant ionic strength. The method of rate measurement is similar to our previous method¹³.

The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate(III) follows first order rate law and the reaction is also first order with respect to the organic substrate. The overall bimolecular rate constants for the oxidation of 1-acetylnaphthalene show fairly concordant values at all concentrations of the reductants. Under the condition of constant ionic strength, the oxidations are directly proportional to

TABLE I—REACTION RATES AND ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) OXIDATION OF AROMATIC KETONES IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

[Hexacyanoferrate(III)]=0.004M, [Ketone]=0.02M
[OH⁻]=0.06M, μ=0.4M, Solvent=30% (V) Methanol-Water

Substrate	k × 10 ⁵ Sec ⁻¹ at °C			E K cal Mole ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] e.u.
	30	35	40		
1-Acetylnaphthalene	7.67	11.51	19.19	15.36	28.74
2-acetylnaphthalene	3.88	6.71	10.51	20.94	11.94
Acetophenone	2.87	5.75	7.67	22.41	5.17

The kinetic data obtained, agree well with derived rate equation. A plot of 1/k versus 1/S passes through origin indicating the absence of complex formation. The reaction involves the interaction between two negatively charged ions or between a negatively charged ion and a polar molecule and thus should correspond to a negative entropy change. This has been found true in many radical reactions¹⁴⁻¹⁵. For the reactions involving the interaction between similarly charged ions, the plots of log k against the reciprocal of dielectric constant would be a straight line, having negative slope. In the present investigation, similar results have also been obtained which substantiate the experimental results.

The observed rates conform to the following order of reactivity (Table 1) 1-acetylnaphthalene > 2-acetylnaphthalene > acetophenone.

The rate of oxidation of 1- and 2-acetylnaphthalene is faster than acetophenone under similar conditions. The greater reactivity of naphthalene ketone may be due to the enhanced stability of the enolic form of the ketone through which the reaction proceeds to give rise to the product. The greater reactivity of 1-acetylnaphthalene over 2-acetylnaphthalene is due to the well established theory that 1-position of naphthalene can tolerate a developing charge to a greater extent than the 2-position¹⁶.

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Stability Constants of Some Bivalent Metal Ions Chelates of Schiff bases Derived from Sulphamethoxy pyridazine

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IN continuation of studies¹ on the sulpha-drugs complexes, the present note embodies the stability constant of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) chelates of Schiff bases derived from sulphamethoxy pyridazine and salicylaldehyde (SMPSA) or *O*-hydroxyacetophenone (SMPHA) in 25% dioxane at 0.1M (NaClO₄) ionic strength at room

temperature (27±0.2°) using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as applied by Irving and Rossotti². The free energy change (ΔG° K cal mole⁻¹) and thermodynamic stabilisation energy (δH) are also calculated.

Experimental

The Schiff bases SMPSA and SMPHA were synthesised by condensing ethanolic solution of sulphamethoxy pyridazine and salicylaldehyde or *O*-hydroxyacetophenone in 1 : 1 ratio. The product obtained was crystallised from acetone.

All the metal ions solution were prepared from the corresponding sulphates, AnalaR (B.D.H.), in double distilled water. Sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid were standardized by usual methods. Chemically pure sodium perchlorate was used to keep the ionic strength constant.

Titration Procedure :

Potentiometric titrations were carried out as reported earlier³. The following mixtures (total volume 40 ml, ionic strength adjusted with 1.0M NaClO₄) keeping 25% (v/v) dioxane medium, were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (0.05M).

(A) 2.0 ml HClO₄ (0.05M), (B) A+10.0 ml Schiff base (0.01M), (C) B+2.5 ml metal ion solution (0.008M).

Results and Discussion

Formation functions \bar{n}_H , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the standard expressions⁴ from the titration curves A, B and C. The log $K_H^\#$ value of the ligands (pH at $\bar{n}_H=0.5$) was evaluated from the plots \bar{n}_H versus pH . The formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL at different pH values. These plots indicate that the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of two for all the metal ions under study, indicating the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (Metal : Ligand) complexes. Applying half integral method log K_1 and log K_2 were obtained and the values are reported in Table 1.

The order of stability constant of bivalent metal complexes with both the Schiff bases is as follows :

The order is in agreement with Irving and Williams order of stability of bivalent metal ions of 3d-series complexes⁴.

The difference between log K_1 and log K_2 (2.40±0.25) show the greater steric hindrance offered by the Schiff bases than coordinated water molecules as observed by Jain and Chaturvedi⁵.